

Halogenation. Part I. Iodination.

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Direct iodination of hydrocarbons, aliphatic or aromatic, has always been a matter of difficulty. This difficulty is attributed to hydriodic acid, produced in the course of the reaction, which reduces the iodo-compound as soon as it is formed. It was suggested that the presence of iodic acid would avoid this difficulty by oxidising the hydriodic acid. Some iodo-compounds have been obtained in this way. Attempts have also been made to bring about direct iodination in presence of other substances. Istrati (*Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1891, (3) 5, 158; *Abs.*, 1891, 60, 1197) prepared di-iodobenzene by the action of a mixture of benzene, iodine and sulphuric acid (*d* 1·84). An iodobenzene sulphonic acid is formed which, along with hydriodic acid, yields sulphur dioxide, water and di-iodobenzene.

Zernoff (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1900, 32, 804) carried out a series of experiments on iodination by means of the chloride and bromide of iodine. Körner and Belasio (*Atti. R. Accad. Lincei*, 1908, (V) 17, ii, 679) iodinated *m*-nitraniline by means of iodine and potassium iodate. Elbs and Jaroslavzev (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1913, (ii) 88, 92) found that iodo-derivatives of aromatic hydrocarbons could be obtained by boiling the latter with iodine and sodium persulphate in glacial acetic acid solution.

Datta and Chatterji (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, 39, 435) succeeded in introducing iodine directly into aromatic hydrocarbons in presence of nitric acid, and obtained good yields of certain iodo-compounds. We find that when nitro-sulphonic acid is added to the mixture of iodine and fuming nitric acid used by Datta and Chatterji, the process takes a shorter time and the yield is improved. The yield is still better if glacial acetic acid is added.

Datta and Chatterji explain the reaction by assuming that nitric acid acts not merely as a catalyst but by oxidising the hydrogen of the hydrocarbon, the nitric acid itself being reduced to lower oxides of nitrogen. According to them the view that the nitro compound is first formed and that the nitro group is then replaced by iodine is untenable: they could not obtain even a trace of iodo-benzene from nitrobenzene by digesting it with iodine for a considerable length of time.

Since a mixture of fuming nitric and nitro-sulphonic acid has been found to be a better nitrating agent than the fuming nitric acid alone (Varma and Kulkarni, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 143) we are inclined to the view that the intermediate formation of the nitro compounds does take place before iodine is introduced into the benzene nucleus. It is the presence of this nascent nitrobenzene that helps the

introduction of iodine into the benzene nucleus. The only proof of this assumption is that a smell of nitrobenzene is perceived when a few c.c. of the nitro-sulphonic acid mixture are added to the reacting mixture, whilst no appreciable quantity of nitrobenzene is found in the end products when iodine in sufficient quantity to form iodo-benzene is present there. The reaction may take place according to the equations,

—the nitrogen peroxide passing out of the sphere of reaction. Evolution of brown oxides of nitrogen was observed when nitric acid alone or the nitro-sulphonic acid mixture was used. The action of acetic acid in increasing the yield of the iodo-compounds can be explained by assuming that it helps the reaction by dissolving iodine.

In order to compare the results obtained by the special method adopted in this paper with those obtained by Datta and Chatterji's method, their experiments with slight modifications have been repeated side by side. It is to be noted that the yield by the method of Datta and Chatterji is improved by the mere addition of glacial acetic acid at the outset of the reaction.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The fuming nitric and nitro-sulphonic acid mixture.

This mixture is prepared by passing a steady current of sulphur dioxide into cold fuming nitric acid of specific

gravity 1.5, until about 50 per cent. of nitro-sulphonic acid is obtained. If the percentage of nitro-sulphonic acid in the mixture is greater than 50 it can be brought down to this value by adding to it the required quantity of fuming nitric acid. A mixture thus prepared was used in the following experiments.

Preparation of Iodobenzene.

1. Benzene (30 c. c.) and finely powdered iodine (25 g.) were put into a clean dry flask fitted with a reflux condenser and kept on a water-bath. To this was added the nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (12 c. c.) in portions of 2 c. c. at a time at intervals of 15 minutes. After the whole of the mixture was added the flask was kept on the water-bath for half an hour; the mixture was then allowed to cool and was treated with very dilute sodium hydroxide solution to remove the unchanged iodine, and washed with water. The heavy liquid was then separated, dehydrated with fused calcium chloride and distilled. The portion distilling at 185-88° was collected separately and was found to be iodobenzene. Yield 15.6 g.

2. Experiment No. 1 was repeated with the addition of glacial acetic acid (3 c. c.) at the beginning of the experiment. The yield of iodobenzene increased to 23.0 g.

3. Experiment No. 1 was repeated using concentrated nitric acid (sp. gr. 1.42) instead of the mixture of fuming nitric and nitro-sulphonic acid. The yield of iodobenzene was 12.5 g. (the experiment of Datta and Chatterji with slight modifications).

4. Experiment No. 3 was repeated with the addition of glacial acetic acid (3 c. c.). The yield of iodobenzene was 17.8 g.

5. A number of experiments have been carried out with the object of finding the proportions that produce the maximum yield of iodobenzene. The results obtained are recorded in the table below:—

Expt.	Benzene.	Iodine.	Acetic acid.	Nitro-sulphonic mixture.	Iodobenzene.
<i>a</i>	30 c. c.	25 g.	Nil.	Nil.	Nil.
<i>b</i>	"	"	3 c. c.	5 c. c.	14.0 g.
<i>c</i>	"	"	"	7 "	17.0
<i>d</i>	"	"	"	9 "	19.5
<i>e</i>	"	"	"	12 "	23.0
<i>f</i>	"	"	"	15 "	22.5
<i>g</i>	"	"	"	18 "	22.0
<i>h</i>	"	"	"	25 "	20.0

Preparation of Iodotoluenes.

6. Toluene (30 c.c.), iodine (25 g.) and glacial acetic acid (3 c. c.) were mixed. The nitro-sulphonic acid mixture (12 c. c.) was added gradually and the whole process was carried out as in Experiment 1. The liquid product (washed and dried) was distilled, and the fraction distilling between 209 and 212° was collected

separately and was found to be a mixture of *ortho*- and *para*-iodotolueness. Yield 21.5 g. A small residue was left in the distilling flask.

7. Experiment No. 6 was repeated using concentrated nitric acid (sp. gr. 1.42). The yield of the two iodotoluenes was found to be 13.5 g.

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